

Supplementary Material to “Towards a common understanding of raw materials education worldwide – An international Qualification Framework for Raw Materials”

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Description

This document contains supplementary material to the above mentioned paper, detailing the level descriptors for all topical areas mentioned in the manuscript both graphically and as tables.

Materials engineering and recycling

Annex - Fig 1: Graphical representation of Level 3 Materials Handling and Recycling.

Level 3 –Materials engineering and Recycling
<p>GENERAL KNOWLEDGE – KNOWS AND UNDERSTANDS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> the basic conditions and dependencies applicable at the department level of his/her organisation; the principles of teamwork under the supervision of a superior; the basic principles of occupational health and safety requirements applicable to assigned tasks.
<p>GENERAL SKILLS – IS ABLE TO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> work in a team; work under pressure; organise his/her own working time; plan and forecast activities.
<p>GENERAL SOCIAL COMPETENCE – IS READY TO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> act according to laws, regulations, best practices and professional ethics; participate in on-the-job demonstrations, training courses and industry fairs.
<p>OCCUPATIONAL KNOWLEDGE – KNOWS AND UNDERSTANDS:</p>

- basic principles of metal production and recycling;
- elementary arithmetic;
- the basic principles of sustainability;
- the concept of raw materials value chain;
- safety principles within the scope of assigned tasks.

OCCUPATIONAL SKILLS – IS ABLE TO:

- work without risk or harm to self and others;
- perform assigned tasks in metal production and recycling operations, in due time and compliance with relevant regulations;
- use correct materials and tools;
- care for the materials and equipment used;
- plan for and notify of needed materials and tools.

OCCUPATIONAL SOCIAL COMPETENCE – IS READY TO:

- assume responsibility for assigned tasks in metal production and recycling operations;
- maintain good interpersonal relations with colleagues, customers and subcontractors;
- comply with work and occupational health and safety regulations applicable in metal production and recycling operations.

The holder of an SQF-RM Level 3 qualification works, for the most part, in the following areas:

- Metals' sorting and scrapping;
- Recycling;
- Smelting.

Example positions requiring qualifications at this level: Operations Assistant; Equipment Operator Assistant; Recycling Labourer; Sorter.

Level 4 - Materials engineering and Recycling

Annex - Fig 2: Graphical representation of Level 4 Materials Handling and Recycling.

Level 4 – Materials engineering and Recycling
<p>GENERAL KNOWLEDGE – KNOWS AND UNDERSTANDS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the basic conditions and dependencies in the structure and activities of the organisation, and the connections to the works being carried out; • the basic principles of safety relating to the occupation and field work; • the principles of teamwork.
<p>GENERAL SKILLS – IS ABLE TO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • effectively motivate colleagues and subordinate employees; • use technical documentation; • improve his/her work performance by analysing observed errors, irregularities; • work under pressure, alone and in a team; • solve problems influencing the scope, quality or timeliness of the tasks being carried out; • comply with organisational rules and confidentiality requirements; • apply occupational health & safety and employment regulations.
<p>GENERAL SOCIAL COMPETENCE – IS READY TO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • direct colleagues and subordinate employees so that they act according to laws, regulations, best practices and professional ethics; • systematically raise professional qualifications through self-improvement, participation in on-the-job demonstrations, training courses and industry fairs; • exercise self-management within the guidelines of work context; • supervise the routine work of others, taking some responsibility for the evaluation and improvement of work or study activities.

OCCUPATIONAL KNOWLEDGE – KNOWS AND UNDERSTANDS:

- elementary geometry, algebra and trigonometry;
- elementary physics and chemistry;
- the basics of metal production and recycling cycles;
- the raw materials value chain and the core principles of sustainability;
- health and safety requirements within the scope of assigned tasks, including plant rescue operations;
- the rules and procedures of quality assurance/quality control systems;
- the provisions and standards in force in metal production and recycling.

OCCUPATIONAL SKILLS – IS ABLE TO:

- use office software (spreadsheet, word processing, email) and IT equipment to organise and report activities;
- perform assigned tasks in metal production and recycling effectively, promptly and in compliance with relevant regulations;
- implement and advance initiatives aiming to safeguard environmental values and ecological services, save energy and water, and manage waste according to best practice;
- assign tasks to subordinate employees diligently and proactively and enforce their timely and suitable performance;
- cooperate with subcontractors;
- plan for and notify of needed materials and tools.

OCCUPATIONAL SOCIAL COMPETENCE – IS READY TO:

- assume responsibility for assigned tasks in metal production and recycling works, in compliance with applicable standards and best practice;
- observe and enforce occupational health and safety regulations;
- keep materials and equipment in a good state of repair and cleanliness;
- establish and maintain good interpersonal relations with subordinate employees, customers and subcontractors.

The holder of an SQF-RM Level 4 qualification works, for the most part, in the following areas:

- Metals' sorting and scrapping;
- Recycling;
- Smelting.

Example positions requiring qualifications at this level: Equipment Operator; Steel Mill Operator; Baler Operator; Loader Operator.

Level 5 - Materials engineering and Recycling

Annex - Fig 3: Graphical representation of Level 5 Materials Handling and Recycling.

Level 5 – Materials engineering and Recycling
<p>GENERAL KNOWLEDGE – KNOWS AND UNDERSTANDS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> the legal provisions relating to metal production and recycling; the methods and dependencies relating to metal production and recycling; the methods and techniques used in metal production and recycling.
<p>GENERAL SKILLS – IS ABLE TO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> implement good practice in handling technical documentation; learn autonomously from textbooks and multimedia tools, and engages in learning discussions in training courses, workshops, fairs, etc.; think analytically, work under time pressure, work in a group, organise his/her own working time.
<p>GENERAL SOCIAL COMPETENCE – IS READY TO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> perform tasks in a responsive, accurate and timely manner; establish and maintain good interpersonal relations and undertake initiatives to improve and increase the effectiveness of the tasks being carried out; train and develop subordinate employees and subcontractors; perform work with accuracy, thoroughness and under the pressure of time.
<p>OCCUPATIONAL KNOWLEDGE – KNOWS AND UNDERSTANDS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> the grounds of metal production and recycling methods; the factors that affect the outcome of metal production and/or recycling; the legal provisions relating to metal production and/or recycling;

- environmental and social best practice in the implementation of metal production and/or recycling activities;
- occupational health and safety regulations applicable to metal production and/or recycling.

OCCUPATIONAL SKILLS – IS ABLE TO:

- autonomously perform tasks following the standard procedures of metal production and/or recycling methods and techniques;
- use IT equipment and metal production and/or recycling documentation software;
- develop and update the technical (e.g. activity planning) and economic outline (e.g. budget) of metal production and/or recycling activities.

OCCUPATIONAL SOCIAL COMPETENCE – IS READY TO:

- file and maintain technical records and documentation of metal production and/or recycling activities in a timely and consistent manner and ensure its good quality;
- comply with regulations, standards and instructions relating to metal production and/or recycling activities;
- systematically raise his/her qualifications by participating in different forms of formal and informal training (autonomous learning included).
- engage with communities, reinforcing mutual trust, respect and effective communication between his/her team and the communities affected by metal production and/or recycling works.

The holder of an SQF-RM Level 5 qualification works, for the most part, in the following areas:

- Metals' sorting and scrapping;
- Recycling;
- Smelting.

Example of a position requiring qualifications at this level: Foreman; Operations Planner; Tracking Coordinator; Welder; Mechanic; Electrician; Senior Laboratory Technician.

Level 6 - Materials engineering and Recycling

Annex - Fig 4::Graphical representation of Level 6 Materials Handling and Recycling.

Level 6 – Materials engineering and Recycling
<p>GENERAL KNOWLEDGE – KNOWS AND UNDERSTANDS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Physical and chemical processes and mechanisms involved in metal production and/or recycling; the complex dependencies between data obtention, data processing, modelling and simulation; his/her professional and ethical responsibilities; communicative English relating to the mineral raw materials sector.
<p>GENERAL SKILLS – IS ABLE TO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> prepare non-standard project solutions in accordance with best practice and the requirements of laws and norms; respond to changes in the external environment of the metal production and/or recycling area; transfer his/her knowledge on metal production and/or recycling methods and techniques to colleagues, subordinate employees and subcontractors; manage teams, plan, forecast and work under pressure; autonomously perform functions and actions relating to project management, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> using IT tools in the design and plan process, launch and execute activities.
<p>GENERAL SOCIAL COMPETENCE – IS READY TO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> assume responsibility, demonstrate innovativeness in the assigned tasks; motivate employees to comply with regulations, best practices and professional ethics; establish and maintain good interpersonal relations with customers and subcontractors;

- undertake initiatives to improve the effectiveness of activities and the financial results of his/her organisation;
- systematically raise professional qualifications through self-improvement and participation in formal and informal training courses;
- autonomously make decisions.

OCCUPATIONAL KNOWLEDGE – KNOWS AND UNDERSTANDS:

- the principles of site and property management, and the corresponding environmental and social obligations;
- the specialised requirements in metal production and/or recycling relating to the applied methods, technologies and standards.

OCCUPATIONAL SKILLS – IS ABLE TO:

- autonomously perform technical functions in metal production and/or recycling, including:
 - supervising smelter operations and/or recycling works;
 - validating smelter/recycling operations;
- coordinate, monitor and validate the work of subcontractors engaged in project implementation;
- identify and select new subcontractors;
- obtain and manage new work orders.

OCCUPATIONAL SOCIAL COMPETENCE – IS READY TO:

- assume responsibility and demonstrate innovativeness in the design and implementation of smelter operations and/or recycling activities;
- apply the legal provisions related to smelter operations and/or recycling recommendations and best practices;
- seeking, listening to and considering community feedback that may be useful in his/her decision-making process;
- assume responsibility for the proper implementation of projects.

The holder of an SQF-RM Level 6 qualification works, for the most part, in the following areas:

- Recycling;
- Smelting.

Example of a position requiring qualifications at this level: Metallurgical Engineer; Materials Engineer; Health & Safety Manager; Recycling Centre Manager.

Level 7 - Materials engineering and Recycling

Annex - Fig 5: Graphical representation of Level 7 Materials Handling and Recycling.

Level 7 – Materials engineering and Recycling
<p>GENERAL KNOWLEDGE – KNOWS AND UNDERSTANDS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> professional and ethical responsibilities of registered professionals; the interdependencies of value chains based on mineral raw materials; the complex dependencies between safety and functionality of the work, economic effectiveness and data obtention, data processing, modelling and simulation; communicative English.
<p>GENERAL SKILLS – IS ABLE TO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> solve complex, non-routine problems of metal production and/or recycling; design and implement metal production and/or recycling operations in accordance with best practice and the requirements of laws and norms; organise working plans and forecasts, and his/her own working time and that of subordinate people; train team members, subordinate employees and subcontractors; independently perform functions and activities relating to contract management, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> using IT tools, writing and talking in English; measure performance and control deviations; motivate team members and subordinate employees.
<p>GENERAL SOCIAL COMPETENCE – IS READY TO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> take responsibility and demonstrate innovativeness; motivate employees to adopt best practices;

- work with and motivate a team under pressure;
- implement best practices and establish good interpersonal relations with all relevant stakeholders;
- undertake initiatives aimed at improving effectiveness and financial results.

OCCUPATIONAL KNOWLEDGE – KNOWS AND UNDERSTANDS:

- the regulations applicable to metal production and/or recycling activities;
- the specific norms and requirements of site and property management applicable in the scope of metal production and/or recycling, and the corresponding environmental and social obligations.

OCCUPATIONAL SKILLS – IS ABLE TO:

- combining different methods and technologies of metal production and/or recycling activities, in a manner consistent with budget and client's goals and requirements;
- manages, controls and assesses metal production and/or recycling activities;
- prepare reports on metal production and/or recycling in a manner consistent with existing reporting codes and norms.

OCCUPATIONAL SOCIAL COMPETENCE – IS READY TO:

- manage metal production and/or recycling activities;
- organise the participation of persons with relevant knowledge, qualifications and competence in preparing contracts;
- fully use his/her specialised knowledge and skills in the design, implementation and follow up of metal production and/or recycling activities;
- assume responsibility for metal production and/or recycling activities;
- properly assess opportunities and counteract threats in the implementation of metal production and/or recycling activities.

The holder of an SQF-RM Level 7 qualification works, for the most part, in the following areas:

- Recycling;
- Smelting.

Example of a position requiring qualifications at this level: Senior Metallurgical Engineer; Senior Materials Engineer, Environmental Coordinator; Recycling Centre Coordinator, Smelting Inspector.

Mineral exploration

Annex - Fig 6: Graphical representation of Level 4 Mineral Exploration

Level 4 – Mineral Exploration
<p>GENERAL KNOWLEDGE – KNOWS AND UNDERSTANDS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> the basic conditions and dependencies in the structure and activities of the organisation, and the connections to the works being carried out; the basic principles of safety relating to the occupation and field work; the principles of teamwork.
<p>GENERAL SKILLS – IS ABLE TO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> effectively motivate colleagues and subordinate employees; use technical documentation; improve his/her work performance by analysing observed errors, irregularities; work under pressure, alone and in a team; organise his/her own working time; plan and forecast activities; solve problems influencing the scope, quality or timeliness of the tasks being carried out; comply with organisational rules and confidentiality requirements; apply occupational health & safety and employment regulations.
<p>GENERAL SOCIAL COMPETENCE – IS READY TO:</p>

- direct colleagues and subordinate employees so that they act according to laws, regulations, best practices and professional ethics;
- systematically raise professional qualifications through self-improvement, participation in on-the-job demonstrations, training courses and industry fairs;
- exercise self-management within the guidelines of work context;
- supervise the routine work of others, taking some responsibility for the evaluation and improvement of work or study activities.

OCCUPATIONAL KNOWLEDGE – KNOWS AND UNDERSTANDS:

- the guiding principles for geoscientific investigations, and the Principles of Geology;
- elementary geometry, algebra and trigonometry;
- principles of mapping and navigation and use of global positioning systems and equipment;
- the raw materials value chain and the core principles of sustainability;
- health and safety requirements within the scope of assigned tasks;
- the rules and procedures of quality assurance/quality control systems;
- the provisions and standards in force in mineral exploration.

OCCUPATIONAL SKILLS – IS ABLE TO:

- use office software (spreadsheet, word processing, email) and IT equipment to organise and report activities;
- perform assigned tasks in mineral exploration programmes effectively, promptly and in compliance with relevant regulations;
- implement and advance initiatives aiming to safeguard environmental values and ecological services, save energy and water, and manage waste according to best practice;
- assign tasks to subordinate employees diligently and proactively and enforce their timely and suitable performance;
- cooperate with subcontractors;
- plan for and notify of needed materials and tools.

OCCUPATIONAL SOCIAL COMPETENCE – IS READY TO:

- assume responsibility for assigned tasks in mineral exploration programmes, in compliance with applicable standards and best practice;
- observe and enforce occupational health and safety regulations;
- keep materials and equipment in a good state of repair and cleanliness;
- establish and maintain good interpersonal relations with local communities, customers, subordinate employees and subcontractors.

The holder of an SQF-RM Level 4 qualification works, for the most part, in the following areas:

- Geophysical or geochemical exploration programmes;
- Exploration drilling;
- Rock sampling;
- Laboratory testing.

Example positions requiring qualifications at this level: Field Assistant; Driller; Driller Assistant; Laboratory Technician; Core Technician; Land Surveyor.

Annex - Fig 7: Graphical representation of Level 5 Mineral Exploration

Level 5 – Mineral Exploration
<p>GENERAL KNOWLEDGE – KNOWS AND UNDERSTANDS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> the legal provisions relating to mineral exploration; the methods and dependencies relating to the development and execution of mineral exploration programmes; the application of methods and techniques used in mineral exploration programmes.
<p>GENERAL SKILLS – IS ABLE TO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> implement good practice in handling technical documentation; learn autonomously from textbooks and multimedia tools, and engages in learning discussions in training courses, workshops, fairs, etc.; think analytically, work under time pressure, work in a group, organise his/her own working time.
<p>GENERAL SOCIAL COMPETENCE – IS READY TO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> perform tasks in a responsive, accurate and timely manner; establish and maintain good interpersonal relations and undertake initiatives to improve and increase the effectiveness of the tasks being carried out; train and develop subordinate employees and subcontractors; perform work with accuracy, thoroughness and under the pressure of time.
<p>OCCUPATIONAL KNOWLEDGE – KNOWS AND UNDERSTANDS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> geological cross sections and maps; the grounds of mineral exploration methods;

- the factors that affect the outcome of mineral exploration programmes;
- the legal provisions relating to mineral exploration programmes and the minerals industry;
- environmental and social best practice in the implementation of mineral exploration activities;
- occupational health and safety regulations applicable to mineral exploration.

OCCUPATIONAL SKILLS – IS ABLE TO:

- autonomously perform tasks following the standard procedures of mineral exploration methods and techniques;
- use IT equipment and mineral exploration design and documentation software;
- develop and update the technical (e.g. activity planning) and economic outline (e.g. budget) of mineral exploration activities.

OCCUPATIONAL SOCIAL COMPETENCE – IS READY TO:

- file and maintain technical records and documentation of mineral exploration activities in a timely and consistent manner and ensure its good quality;
- comply with regulations, standards and instructions relating to mineral exploration activities;
- systematically raise his/her qualifications by participating in different forms of formal and informal training (autonomous learning included).
- engage with communities, reinforcing mutual trust, respect and effective communication between his/her team and the communities affected by mineral exploration works.

The holder of an SQF-RM Level 5 qualification works, for the most part, in the following areas:

- Geophysical or geochemical exploration programmes;
- Exploration drilling;
- Laboratory testing;
- Classification and evaluation of mineral deposits.

Example of a position requiring qualifications at this level: Drilling Supervisor; Foreman; Senior Laboratory Technician; Operations Planner; Permitting Manager.

Level 6 - Mineral Exploration

Annex - Fig 8: Graphical representation of Level 6 Mineral Exploration

Level 6 – Mineral Exploration
<p>GENERAL KNOWLEDGE – KNOWS AND UNDERSTANDS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> geological processes in space and time and mechanisms involved; the complex dependencies between data obtention, data processing, modelling and simulation; his/her professional and ethical responsibilities; communicative English relating to the mineral exploration sector.
<p>GENERAL SKILLS – IS ABLE TO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> use geoscience information to generate predictive models; prepare non-standard project solutions in accordance with best practice and the requirements of laws and norms; respond to changes in the external environment of the mineral exploration sector; transfer his/her knowledge on mineral exploration methods and techniques to colleagues, subordinate employees and subcontractors; manage teams, plan, forecast and work under pressure; autonomously perform functions and actions relating to project management, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> using IT tools in the design and plan process, launch and execute exploration activities.
<p>GENERAL SOCIAL COMPETENCE – IS READY TO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> assume responsibility, demonstrate innovativeness in the assigned tasks; motivate employees to comply with regulations, best practices and professional ethics; establish and maintain good interpersonal relations with customers and subcontractors;

- undertake initiatives to improve the effectiveness of projects and the financial results of his/her organisation;
- systematically raise professional qualifications through self-improvement and participation in formal and informal training courses;
- autonomously make decisions.

OCCUPATIONAL KNOWLEDGE – KNOWS AND UNDERSTANDS:

- the principles of the investment process, including the rights and obligations of its participants;
- the principles of site and property management, and the corresponding environmental and social obligations;
- the specialised requirements in mineral exploration relating to the applied methods, technologies and standards.

OCCUPATIONAL SKILLS – IS ABLE TO:

- autonomously perform technical functions in mineral exploration, including:
 - designing and supervising exploration works;
 - validating the design of exploration programmes;
- coordinate, monitor and validate the work of subcontractors engaged in project implementation;
- identify and select new subcontractors;
- obtain and manage new work orders.

OCCUPATIONAL SOCIAL COMPETENCE – IS READY TO:

- assume responsibility and demonstrate innovativeness in the design and implementation of mineral exploration programmes;
- apply the legal provisions related to mineral exploration and industry recommendations and best practices;
- seeking, listening to and considering community feedback that may be useful in his/her decision-making process;
- assume responsibility for the proper implementation of projects.

The holder of an SQF-RM Level 6 qualification works, for the most part, in the following areas:

- Geophysical or geochemical exploration programmes;
- Exploration drilling;
- Laboratory testing;
- Classification and evaluation of mineral deposits.

Example of a position requiring qualifications at this level: Geophysicist; Exploration Geologist; Project Manager; Geotechnical Engineer; Geospatial Analyst; Mine Engineer.

Annex - Fig 9: Graphical representation of Level 7 Mineral Exploration

Level 7 – Mineral Exploration
<p>GENERAL KNOWLEDGE – KNOWS AND UNDERSTANDS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • professional and ethical responsibilities of professional geoscientists; • the interdependencies of value chains based on mineral raw materials; • the complex dependencies between economic effectiveness and data obtention, processing, modelling and simulation; • the complex dependencies between safety and functionality of the work, economic effectiveness and data obtention, data processing, modelling and simulation; • communicative English.
<p>GENERAL SKILLS – IS ABLE TO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • solve complex, non-routine problems of mineral exploration programmes; • design unique mineral exploration projects in accordance with best practice and the requirements of laws and norms; • organise working plans and forecasts, and his/her own working time and that of subordinate people; • train team members, subordinate employees and subcontractors; • independently perform functions and activities relating to contract management, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ using IT tools, ○ writing and talking in English; ○ measure performance and control deviations; • motivate team members and subordinate employees.
<p>GENERAL SOCIAL COMPETENCE – IS READY TO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • take responsibility and demonstrate innovativeness;

- motivate employees to adopt best practices;
- work with and motivate a team under pressure;
- implement best practices and establish good interpersonal relations with all relevant stakeholders;
- undertake initiatives aimed at improving effectiveness and financial results.

OCCUPATIONAL KNOWLEDGE – KNOWS AND UNDERSTANDS:

- the provisions of exploration contracts, including the rights and obligations of its participants;
- in depth, the regulations applicable to mineral exploration programmes;
- the specific norms and requirements of site and property management applicable in the scope of a contract, and the corresponding environmental and social obligations;
- the application of methods and techniques of mineral exploration to improve the processes of mineral extraction and processing.

OCCUPATIONAL SKILLS – IS ABLE TO:

- design mineral exploration programmes, using different methods and technologies in a manner consistent with budget and client's goals and requirements;
- manages, controls and assesses the implementation of exploration programmes;
- prepare reports of mineral exploration programmes in a manner consistent with existing reporting codes and norms;
- prepare mineral exploration contracts and the corresponding technical documentation.

OCCUPATIONAL SOCIAL COMPETENCE – IS READY TO:

- design and manage mineral exploration programmes;
- organise the participation of persons with relevant knowledge, qualifications and competence in preparing contracts;
- fully use his/her specialised knowledge and skills in the design, implementation and follow up of exploration programmes;
- assume responsibility for mineral exploration programmes;
- properly assess opportunities and counteract threats in the implementation of exploration programmes.

The holder of an SQF-RM Level 7 qualification works, for the most part, in the following areas:

- Geophysical or geochemical exploration programmes;
- Exploration drilling;
- Laboratory testing;
- Classification and evaluation of mineral deposits.

Example of a position requiring qualifications at this level: Senior Exploration Geologist; Senior Project Manager; Mineral Potential Supervisor; Geologists Supervisor.

Mineral extraction and processing

Annex - Fig 10: Graphical representation of Level 3 Mineral Extraction and Processing

Level 3 – Mineral Extraction and Processing
<p>GENERAL KNOWLEDGE – KNOWS AND UNDERSTANDS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> the basic conditions and dependencies applicable at the department level of his/her organisation; the principles of teamwork under the supervision of a superior; the basic principles of occupational health and safety requirements applicable to assigned tasks.
<p>GENERAL SKILLS – IS ABLE TO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> work in a team; work under pressure; organise his/her own working time; plan and forecast activities.
<p>GENERAL SOCIAL COMPETENCE – IS READY TO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> act according to laws, regulations, best practices and professional ethics; participate in on-the-job demonstrations, training courses and industry fairs.
<p>OCCUPATIONAL KNOWLEDGE – KNOWS AND UNDERSTANDS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> basic principles of mineral extraction and processing; elementary geology and arithmetic; the basic principles of sustainability; the concept of raw materials value chain;

- safety principles within the scope of assigned tasks.

OCCUPATIONAL SKILLS – IS ABLE TO:

- work without risk or harm to self and others;
- perform assigned tasks in mineral extraction and processing operations, in due time and compliance with relevant regulations;
- use correct materials and tools;
- care for the materials and equipment used;
- plan for and notify of needed materials and tools.

OCCUPATIONAL SOCIAL COMPETENCE – IS READY TO:

- assume responsibility for assigned tasks in mineral extraction and processing operations;
- maintain good interpersonal relations with colleagues, customers and subcontractors;
- comply with work and occupational health and safety regulations applicable in mineral extraction and processing operations.

The holder of an SQF-RM Level 3 qualification works, for the most part, in the following areas:

- Mining and quarrying;
- Mineral processing;
- Mine surveying;
- Tunnelling.

Example positions requiring qualifications at this level: Process Operator; Equipment Operator Assistant; Underground Driller Helper; Mine Surveyor Assistant; General Labourer.

Level 4 - Mineral Extraction and Processing

Annex - Fig 11: Graphical representation of Level 4 Mineral Extraction and Processing

Level 4 – Mineral Extraction and Processing
<p>GENERAL KNOWLEDGE – KNOWS AND UNDERSTANDS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> the basic conditions and dependencies in the structure and activities of the organisation, and the connections to the works being carried out; the basic principles of safety relating to the occupation and field work; the principles of teamwork.
<p>GENERAL SKILLS – IS ABLE TO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> effectively motivate colleagues and subordinate employees; use technical documentation; improve his/her work performance by analysing observed errors, irregularities; work under pressure, alone and in a team; solve problems influencing the scope, quality or timeliness of the tasks being carried out; comply with organisational rules and confidentiality requirements; apply occupational health & safety and employment regulations.
<p>GENERAL SOCIAL COMPETENCE – IS READY TO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> direct colleagues and subordinate employees so that they act according to laws, regulations, best practices and professional ethics; systematically raise professional qualifications through self-improvement, participation in on-the-job demonstrations, training courses and industry fairs; exercise self-management within the guidelines of work context;

- supervise the routine work of others, taking some responsibility for the evaluation and improvement of work or study activities.

OCCUPATIONAL KNOWLEDGE – KNOWS AND UNDERSTANDS:

- elementary geometry, algebra and trigonometry;
- elementary physics and chemistry;
- elementary geology and the basics of the mining cycle;
- the raw materials value chain and the core principles of sustainability;
- health and safety requirements within the scope of assigned tasks, including mine/plant rescue operations;
- the rules and procedures of quality assurance/quality control systems;
- the provisions and standards in force in mineral extraction and processing.

OCCUPATIONAL SKILLS – IS ABLE TO:

- use office software (spreadsheet, word processing, email) and IT equipment to organise and report activities;
- perform assigned tasks in mineral extraction and processing effectively, promptly and in compliance with relevant regulations;
- implement and advance initiatives aiming to safeguard environmental values and ecological services, save energy and water, and manage waste according to best practice;
- assign tasks to subordinate employees diligently and proactively and enforce their timely and suitable performance;
- cooperate with subcontractors;
- plan for and notify of needed materials and tools.

OCCUPATIONAL SOCIAL COMPETENCE – IS READY TO:

- assume responsibility for assigned tasks in mineral extraction and processing works, in compliance with applicable standards and best practice;
- observe and enforce occupational health and safety regulations;
- keep materials and equipment in a good state of repair and cleanliness;
- establish and maintain good interpersonal relations with subordinate employees, customers and subcontractors.

The holder of an SQF-RM Level 4 qualification works, for the most part, in the following areas:

- Mining and quarrying;
- Mineral processing;
- Mine surveying.

Example positions requiring qualifications at this level: Mine Surveyor; Blaster; Excavator/Dumper/Crusher Operator; Underground Driller; Assay Lab Technician.

Level 5 - Mineral Extraction and Processing

Annex - Fig 12: Graphical representation of Level 5 Mineral Extraction and Processing

Level 5 – Mineral Extraction and Processing
<p>GENERAL KNOWLEDGE – KNOWS AND UNDERSTANDS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the legal provisions relating to mineral extraction and/or processing; • the methods and dependencies relating to mineral extraction and/or processing; • the methods and techniques used in mineral extraction and/or processing.
<p>GENERAL SKILLS – IS ABLE TO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • implement good practice in handling technical documentation; • learn autonomously from textbooks and multimedia tools, and engages in learning discussions in training courses, workshops, fairs, etc.; • think analytically, work under time pressure, work in a group, organise his/her own working time.
<p>GENERAL SOCIAL COMPETENCE – IS READY TO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • perform tasks in a responsive, accurate and timely manner; • establish and maintain good interpersonal relations and undertake initiatives to improve and increase the effectiveness of the tasks being carried out; • train and develop subordinate employees and subcontractors; • perform work with accuracy, thoroughness and under the pressure of time.
<p>OCCUPATIONAL KNOWLEDGE – KNOWS AND UNDERSTANDS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the grounds of mineral extraction and/or processing methods; • the factors that affect the outcome of mineral extraction and/or processing; • the legal provisions relating to mineral extraction and/or processing;

- environmental and social best practice in the implementation of mineral extraction and/or processing activities;
- occupational health and safety regulations applicable to mineral extraction and/or processing.

OCCUPATIONAL SKILLS – IS ABLE TO:

- autonomously perform tasks following the standard procedures of mineral extraction and/or processing methods and techniques;
- use IT equipment and mineral extraction and/or processing documentation software;
- develop and update the technical (e.g. activity planning) and economic outline (e.g. budget) of mineral extraction and/or processing activities.

OCCUPATIONAL SOCIAL COMPETENCE – IS READY TO:

- file and maintain technical records and documentation of mineral extraction and/or processing activities in a timely and consistent manner and ensure its good quality;
- comply with regulations, standards and instructions relating to mineral extraction and/or processing activities;
- systematically raise his/her qualifications by participating in different forms of formal and informal training (autonomous learning included).
- engage with communities, reinforcing mutual trust, respect and effective communication between his/her team and the communities affected by mineral extraction and/or processing works.

The holder of an SQF-RM Level 5 qualification works, for the most part, in the following areas:

- Mining and quarrying;
- Mineral processing;
- Mine surveying.

Example of a position requiring qualifications at this level: Foreman; Operations Planner; Welder; Mechanic; Development Miner; Electrician; Senior Laboratory Technician.

Level 6 - Mineral Extraction and Processing

Annex - Fig 13: Graphical representation of Level 6 Mineral Extraction and Processing

Level 6 – Mineral Extraction and Processing
<p>GENERAL KNOWLEDGE – KNOWS AND UNDERSTANDS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> geological processes in space and time and mechanisms involved; the complex dependencies between data obtention, data processing, modelling and simulation; his/her professional and ethical responsibilities; communicative English relating to the mineral raw materials sector.
<p>GENERAL SKILLS – IS ABLE TO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> use geoscience information to generate predictive models; prepare non-standard project solutions in accordance with best practice and the requirements of laws and norms; respond to changes in the external environment of the mineral extraction and/or processing area; transfer his/her knowledge on mineral extraction and/or processing methods and techniques to colleagues, subordinate employees and subcontractors; manage teams, plan, forecast and work under pressure; autonomously perform functions and actions relating to project management, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> using IT tools in the design and plan process, launch and execute activities.
<p>GENERAL SOCIAL COMPETENCE – IS READY TO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> assume responsibility, demonstrate innovativeness in the assigned tasks; motivate employees to comply with regulations, best practices and professional ethics; establish and maintain good interpersonal relations with customers and subcontractors;

- undertake initiatives to improve the effectiveness of activities and the financial results of his/her organisation;
- systematically raise professional qualifications through self-improvement and participation in formal and informal training courses;
- autonomously make decisions.

OCCUPATIONAL KNOWLEDGE – KNOWS AND UNDERSTANDS:

- the principles of site and property management, and the corresponding environmental and social obligations;
- the specialised requirements in mineral extraction and/or processing relating to the applied methods, technologies and standards.

OCCUPATIONAL SKILLS – IS ABLE TO:

- autonomously perform technical functions in mineral extraction and/or processing, including:
 - designing and supervising mining works;
 - validating the design of mining plans / mineral processing operations;
- coordinate, monitor and validate the work of subcontractors engaged in project implementation;
- identify and select new subcontractors;
- obtain and manage new work orders.

OCCUPATIONAL SOCIAL COMPETENCE – IS READY TO:

- assume responsibility and demonstrate innovativeness in the design and implementation of extraction/mineral processing activities;
- apply the legal provisions related to mineral extraction and/or processing recommendations and best practices;
- seeking, listening to and considering community feedback that may be useful in his/her decision-making process;
- assume responsibility for the proper implementation of projects.

The holder of an SQF-RM Level 6 qualification works, for the most part, in the following areas:

- Mining and quarrying;
- Mineral processing;
- Mine surveying.

Example of a position requiring qualifications at this level: Mine Geologist; Mine Engineer; Geotechnical Engineer; Metallurgical Engineer; Health & Safety Manager.

Level 7 - Mineral Extraction and Processing

Annex - Fig 14: Graphical representation of Level 7 Mineral Extraction and Processing

Level 7 – Mineral Extraction and Processing
<p>GENERAL KNOWLEDGE – KNOWS AND UNDERSTANDS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> professional and ethical responsibilities of professional geoscientists; the interdependencies of value chains based on mineral raw materials; the complex dependencies between economic effectiveness and data obtention, processing, modelling and simulation; the complex dependencies between safety and functionality of the work, economic effectiveness and data obtention, data processing, modelling and simulation; communicative English.
<p>GENERAL SKILLS – IS ABLE TO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> solve complex, non-routine problems of mineral extraction and/or processing; design and implement mineral extraction and/or processing operations in accordance with best practice and the requirements of laws and norms; organise working plans and forecasts, and his/her own working time and that of subordinate people; train team members, subordinate employees and subcontractors; independently perform functions and activities relating to contract management, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> using IT tools, writing and talking in English; measure performance and control deviations; motivate team members and subordinate employees.
<p>GENERAL SOCIAL COMPETENCE – IS READY TO:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> take responsibility and demonstrate innovativeness;

- motivate employees to adopt best practices;
- work with and motivate a team under pressure;
- implement best practices and establish good interpersonal relations with all relevant stakeholders;
- undertake initiatives aimed at improving effectiveness and financial results.

OCCUPATIONAL KNOWLEDGE – KNOWS AND UNDERSTANDS:

- the provisions of mining contracts, including the rights and obligations of its participants;
- the regulations applicable to mineral extraction and/or processing activities;
- the specific norms and requirements of site and property management applicable in the scope of a mining contract, and the corresponding environmental and social obligations.

OCCUPATIONAL SKILLS – IS ABLE TO:

- combining different methods and technologies of plan mineral extraction and/or processing activities, in a manner consistent with budget and client's goals and requirements;
- manages, controls and assesses mineral extraction and/or processing activities;
- prepare reports on mineral extraction and/or processing in a manner consistent with existing reporting codes and norms.

OCCUPATIONAL SOCIAL COMPETENCE – IS READY TO:

- manage mineral extraction and/or processing activities;
- organise the participation of persons with relevant knowledge, qualifications and competence in preparing contracts;
- fully use his/her specialised knowledge and skills in the design, implementation and follow up of mineral extraction and/or processing activities;
- assume responsibility for mineral extraction and/or processing activities;
- properly assess opportunities and counteract threats in the implementation of mineral extraction and/or processing activities.

The holder of an SQF-RM Level 7 qualification works, for the most part, in the following areas:

- Geophysical or geochemical exploration programmes;
- Classification and evaluation of mineral deposits.
- Mining and quarrying;
- Mineral processing;
- Management.

Example of a position requiring qualifications at this level: Senior Mine Geologist; Senior Mine Engineer, Environmental Coordinator; Metallurgical Engineer; Mine/Quarry Manager.